

Thought code, that coded thoughts.

This is thought code, made out of binary 1ones and 0zeros, that construct the thought of an individual, into morse code road, where the code goes as followed:

- Binary base of rathered 1's (ones) or 0 (zero's), where a 1 has one quality of that of positive done, and a 0 has the 0zeroed one1 quality of that of negative (?nonedone), and that is why it is summed.
- Pair-base of either 1-0 or 0-1 which make 0-zero0ed and either 1-on1ed.
- Code dash of specifically either 1_ or _0, which make a pash, of code spledash, ever a dash, away, from code_pad_lash...
- Code (duo(pairedzero)), forever a hero...
- Code symbol...
- Code number...
- Code cancel...
- Code Capital...
- Code lower...
- Code case^...
- Code beta,...
- Code Stop.>. ...
- Code>go ...
- Code red...
- Code enter...
- Code exit...
- Code lock...
- Code key...
- Code trill...
- CodeBLEET...
- Code score...
- CodeBlank...
- Code colour...
- Code !exclaim?!...
- Code ?question!>?...
- Code ans!wer...
- Code _d_o_w_n_ ...
- Code seen ... me? ...
- The morse code rather, of a dot ->. or a ...?>!
- Code arrow...
- Code {not} !.. contained ...
- Code plus ...+...but ...
- Code minus - ... +- ... yeah no ...

A cloud is a thought, and thought is code/

There is:

- Moment code...
- Position code...
- Length code...
- Distance code...
- Area code...
- Angle code...
- Volume code...
- Degree code...
- 4th wall code...
- Extra code...
- Code extra...
- Sky code...
- Black code... -> Black model void, point black...
- Blue code... -> Blue model void, point blue...
- Code channel...
- Channel code...
- Black channel, -> channel back...
- Code wipe...
- Wipe code...
- Code PointBlank...
- Code idea...
- Idea code...

So a thought is extra, from an unextra-d extra...